

Research Note

Trend of Pathogenic *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* Occurrences in Bivalve Molluscs Harvested in Sardinian Coastal Environments Between 2011 and 2018

Giuseppe Tedde¹, Giuseppa Lorenzoni¹, Domenico Meloni^{2,*}, Sara Salza¹, Rita Melillo¹, Riccardo Bazzardi¹, Simona Cau¹, Tiziana Tedde¹, Gabriella Piras¹, Maria Teresa Uda¹, Francesca Leoni³, Giuseppe Esposito⁴, Sebastiano Virgilio¹, Alessandro Graziano Mudadu¹

¹ Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Della Sardegna, Struttura Complessa di Microbiologia e Ispezione Degli Alimenti di Origine Animale, Via Duca Degli Abruzzi 8, 07100 Sassari, Italy

² Dipartimento di Medicina Veterinaria, Università Degli Studi di Sassari, Via Vienna 2, 07100 Sassari, Italy

³ Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Umbria e Delle Marche, LNR per le Contaminazioni Batteriologiche dei Molluschi Bivalvi, Sezione di Ancona, Via Cupa di Posatora 3, 60131 Ancona, Italy

⁴ Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale del Piemonte, Liguria e Valle d'Aosta, Via Bologna 148, 10154 Torino, Italy

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to evaluate *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* occurrences in bivalve molluscs harvested from Sardinian coastal environments between 2013 and 2015. The prevalence of pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates is based on the detection of the two major virulence genes thermostable direct hemolysin (*tdh*) and thermolabile hemolysin (*trh*). To assess changes between 2011 and 2018 in the prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* in bivalve molluscs, we compared our results with those of previous investigations. In total, 2,933 samples were collected: 1,079 in 2013, 1,288 in 2014, and 566 in 2015. The mean prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* in shellfish was 3.5% in 2013, 1.7% in 2014, and 3.5% in 2015. The highest percentage of positive samples in 2013 and 2014 was observed in clams (3.5% and 2.7%, respectively), whereas in 2015, it was reported in oysters (15.1%). By comparing the sampling period of 2011–2014 with that of 2015–2018, an increase in the prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* was observed in shellfish ($p < 0.05$). In parallel, 208 potentially enteropathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* strains were identified through the years 2011–2018 and, in particular, 10 *trh*+ and six *tdh*+ isolates. Our present study provides information regarding trends of *V. parahaemolyticus* occurrences in bivalve molluscs harvested from Sardinian coastal environments between 2011 and 2018 suggesting that the prevalence varies depending on the sampling period and shellfish species.

Globally, vibrio species are routinely recovering from estuarine, marine, and coastal environments (Joseph et al., 1982; Oh et al., 2011; Letchumanan et al., 2014). Approximately, 12 *Vibrio* spp. can lead to vibriosis illness in humans primarily caused by *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Vibrio vulnificus*, and *Vibrio cholerae* (Robert-Pillot et al., 2014; Silva et al., 2018; Park et al., 2019). Among these, *V. parahaemolyticus* is the most common and can cause severe gastroenteritis, septicemia, and even death (Boyd et al., 2008; Ceccarelli et al., 2013). This curved rod, gram-negative, halophilic bacterium is broadly disseminated in seawater, seafloor sediments, and aquaculture systems. It is often found in a free-swimming state and supplied by a single polar flagellum or attached to inert and animate surfaces, including zooplankton, fish, shellfish, or any suspended matter underwater (Joseph et al., 1982; Oh et al., 2011; Letchumanan et al., 2014; Elmahdi et al., 2016; Lopatek et al., 2018). Eating raw or undercooked

seafood, especially bivalve molluscs, can increase the risk of exposure to *V. parahaemolyticus* contaminating seafood and of developing seafood-borne illnesses (Elmahdi et al., 2016; Kang et al., 2017; Kim et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2017; Park et al., 2018; Ashrafudoulla et al., 2021). *V. parahaemolyticus* is the primary cause of human gastrointestinal disorders in many countries, including the USA, Japan, and Korea (Wang et al., 2015; Elmahdi et al., 2016; Kang et al., 2017; Izan et al., 2018; Ashrafudoulla et al., 2020). Conversely, human illnesses caused by *V. parahaemolyticus* have rarely been described in the European Union (EU) (Martinez-Urtaza et al., 2004; Quilici et al., 2005; Ottaviani et al., 2012). This should be due that vibriosis is not a notifiable disease in the EU. However, in 2021, three food-borne outbreaks (one strong evidence outbreak) caused by *V. parahaemolyticus* were reported in the EU (EFSA & ECDC, 2022). In the EU, a total of 10 human cases, which was 0.03% of the total number

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: dmeloni@uniss.it (D. Meloni).

of cases attributed to foodborne agents, were attributed to *V. parahaemolyticus*, and eventually no hospitalizations and deaths (EFSA & ECDC, 2022). Only the *V. parahaemolyticus* strains carrying specific virulence factors are considered potentially pathogenic such as the species-specific markers *toxR* the gene encoding the thermolabile hemolysin (*tlh*) (Rojas et al., 2011; Ashrafudoulla et al., 2019) and other genes encoding thermostable direct hemolysin (*tdh*) and *tdh*-related hemolysin (*trh*) are pathogenic in humans (Xu et al., 2016; Xie et al., 2017). Other genes as extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (*blaTEM*), biofilm *VP950* (encoding a lipoprotein-related protein), pathogenicity island-2 (*VPaI-2*), *VPaI3*, *VPaI-4*, *VPaI-6*, and *VPaI-7*; T3SS (type III secretion systems); and T6SS (type VI secretion systems) (Rojas et al., 2011; Letchumanan et al., 2014). The virulence of *V. parahaemolyticus* is primarily attributed to the occurrence of two primary genes that are enteropathogenicity ally correlated: *tdh* and *trh* (Kang et al., 2017; Xie et al., 2017), which is largely due to their connection with the enterotoxigenic, hemolytic, and cytotoxic activities of *V. parahaemolyticus* in host cells (Lopatek et al., 2018; Prabhakaran et al., 2020). Pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* have one or both of the *tdh* or *trh* genes (Deepanjali et al., 2005; West et al., 2013; Raghunath, 2005; Ashrafudoulla et al., 2019). Thus, the occurrence of *tdh*- and/or *trh*-positive *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates in bivalve molluscs, particularly oysters, is a major public health risk (Wang et al., 2015; Xie et al., 2017). Previous studies have shown that 90–99.8% of clinical *V. parahaemolyticus* strains are positive for the *tdh* and/or *trh* genes, whereas only 0.2–10% of environmental strains harbor these toxin genes (Jiang et al., 2014; Silva et al., 2018; Ahmed et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2018). Therefore, *tdh* and *trh* genes are widely used to confirm the pathogenicity of *V. parahaemolyticus* (Martinez-Urtaza et al., 2018). *V. parahaemolyticus* persists at 5–45°C and grows substantially when seawater temperatures are over 14–19°C (Lamon, Consolati, et al., 2019), explaining its prevalence in the summer and autumn seasons (Lamon, Bastardo, et al., 2019). Under adverse environmental conditions (i.e. in winter), *V. parahaemolyticus* may be undetectable (Su & Liu, 2007; Passalacqua et al., 2016; Sferlazzo et al., 2018). Pathogenic strains may survive colder conditions in marine sediments or they would be the first strains to appear in coastal environments and are slowly overlapped by nonpathogenic isolates, as the water warms (DePaola et al., 2003; Rodriguez-Castro et al., 2010). Understanding *V. parahaemolyticus* occurrences in bivalve molluscs is mandatory for food safety purposes; to determine reveal and decrease the occurrence of outbreaks caused by *V. parahaemolyticus*, it is necessary to study the distribution of potentially pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates in aquatic products. Italy is the third largest EU producer of bivalve molluscs in the EU after Spain and France (EUMOFA, 2023), and Sardinia is a primary resource for the Italian shellfish aquaculture (Sferlazzo et al., 2018). To the best of our knowledge, there are few studies on *V. parahaemolyticus* in shellfish samples collected in Sardinian coastal environments. At present, long-term studies on the occurrence and distribution of pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* are limited in Italy. The collection and analysis of long-term data are essential for the development of regional and national intervention and control programs. Therefore, the main objective of the present study was to determine the occurrence of *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates in bivalve molluscs harvested from Sardinian coastal environments from 2013 to 2015. In addition, we investigated the virulence of *V. parahaemolyticus* strains based on the presence of two primary virulence genes, *tdh* and *trh*. Finally, we aimed to assess the changes in 2011–2018 in the prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* in different bivalve molluscs (mussels, oysters, and clams), investigated areas (Sassari, Oristano, Nuoro, and Cagliari provinces), and sampling periods (2011–2014 vs. 2015–2018) to identify possible risks to human health.

Sampling. From 2013 to 2015, shellfish samples (n. 2,933; 2013 = 1,079; 2014 = 1,288; 2015 = 566; Table 1) were collected from several harvesting areas located in the four provinces (Sassari, Oristano, Nuoro, and Cagliari) of Sardinia (Italy) as part of a regional

plan for official control of the production and marketing of live bivalve and gastropod molluscs (Fig. 1). Samples of three shellfish species were included in this study: Mediterranean mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*, no. 2,003), grooved carpet shells (*Ruditapes decussatus*, no. 544), and Pacific cupped oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*, no. 386). Sampling was performed bimonthly using the veterinary services of the National Health System. The samples were shipped to the laboratories of the Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Sardegna (IZS) in Sassari and analyzed within 24 h of harvesting. Depending on the shell size, 15–30 molluscs from each sample group were randomly selected for microbiological analysis according to ISO method 6887-3:2003 (ISO, 2003).

Detection of *V. parahaemolyticus*. The samples were analyzed for *Vibrio* detection as previously described by Lorenzoni et al. (2021). *Vibrio* spp. were detected in thiosulfate citrate bile and sucrose agar (TCBS; Oxoid) and triphenyltetrazolium chloride soya tryptone agar (TSAT; Oxoid) plates incubated at 37°C for 24 ± 3 h. Typical colonies of *V. parahaemolyticus* on TCBS and TSAT were randomly selected and streaked on 2% NaCl tryptone soya agar (SNA; Oxoid) plates incubated at 30°C for 24 h. Colonies were submitted to Gram staining, oxidase activity, and biochemical tests by the VITEK 2 compact system (bioMérieux) to confirm *Vibrio* identification. All isolates identified as *V. parahaemolyticus* by the VITEK 2 were subjected to polymerase chain reaction (PCR) analysis to detect potentially enteropathogenic strains and to determine their pathogenicity.

Detection of potentially enteropathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* strains. Potentially enteropathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates were identified using a PCR assay targeting the *VP-toxR* gene (Table 2) according to the protocols of Bej et al. (1999). Controls were included for each PCR run. The negative control was a *Listeria* strain from the IZS collection, and the positive controls were *V. parahaemolyticus* ATCC 17802 (*toxR*+, *tdh*-, *trh*+) and ATCC 43996 (*toxR*+, *tdh*+, *trh*-). All PCR amplifications were performed in a PCR Express Thermocycler (Thermo-Hybrid) as previously described (Bej et al., 1999; Lorenzoni et al., 2021).

Determination of pathogenic strains of *V. parahaemolyticus*. The pathogenicity of *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates was determined by PCR targeting the virulence genes *tdh* and *trh* (Table 2) according to the protocols of Bej et al. (1999). A negative control (*Listeria* strain from the IZS collection) and two *V. parahaemolyticus* positive controls (ATCC 43996, *toxR*+, *tdh*+, *trh*-; ATCC 17802, *toxR*+, *tdh*-, *trh*+) were included in each PCR run. All PCR amplifications were performed in a PCR Express Thermocycler (Thermo-Hybrid) as previously described (Bej et al., 1999; Lorenzoni et al., 2021).

Statistical analysis. Differences in the occurrence of *V. parahaemolyticus* in different bivalve molluscs (Mediterranean mussels, Pacific cupped oysters, and grooved carpet shells), investigated areas (Sassari, Oristano, Nuoro, and Cagliari provinces), and sampling periods (2011–2014 vs. 2015–2018) were assessed using chi-square tests (Social Science Statistics, 2023). A p value of less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) was defined as statistically significant.

Results and discussion

Detection of *V. parahaemolyticus*. The mean prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* in shellfish was 3.5% in 2013 (38 positive out of 1,079 collected samples), 1.7% in 2014 (22 positive out of 1,288 collected samples), and 3.5% in 2015 (20 positive out of 566 collected samples) (Table 1). The highest prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* was reported for grooved carpet shells (3.6%). Of the four investigated provinces, Oristano had the highest percentage of positive samples (3.7%). Eighty *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates were identified using biochemical tests and tested using PCR assays for the detection of potentially enteropathogenic strains.

Table 1
Positive samples/total and prevalence (%) of *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* in shellfish

Year	Samples	Positive samples/sampled units (%)							
		Provinces				Species			
		Sassari	Nuoro	Oristano	Cagliari	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i>	<i>R. decussatus</i>	<i>C. gigas</i>	Total
2013	1,079	12/412 (2.9)	2/110 (1.8)	12/185 (6.4)	12/372 (3.2)	27/760 (3.5)	10/279 (3.5)	1/40 (2.5)	38/1,079 (3.5)
2014	1,288	7/357 (1.8)	2/179 (1.1)	5/253 (1.9)	8/481 (1.6)	15/788 (1.9)	5/220 (2.2)	2/280 (0.7)	22/1,288 (1.7)
2015	566	8/181 (4.4)	7/85 (8.2)	2/71 (2.8)	3/229 (1.3)	5/455 (1)	5/45 (11.1)	10/66 (15.1)	20/566 (3.5)
Total	2,933	27/968 (2.7)	11/374 (2.9)	19/509 (3.7)	23/1,082 (2.1)	47/2,003 (2.3)	20/544 (3.6)	13/386 (3.3)	80/2,933 (2.7)

Figure 1. Harvesting areas located in the four provinces (Sassari, Oristano, Nuoro and Cagliari) of Sardinia (Italy) and sampled from 2013 to 2015 as part of the regional plan of official control of production and marketing of live bivalve and gastropod molluscs. *Harvesting areas of the municipality of Olbia are included in the province of Sassari; ** Harvesting areas of the municipality of Lanusei are included in the province of Nuoro; *** Harvesting areas of the municipality of Carbonia are included in the province of Cagliari.

Table 2
Primer and probe sequences used for the investigation of *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*

Primer and probe	Sequence	Target
toxR (F)	GTC TTC TGA CGC AAT CGT TG	toxR
toxR (R)	ATA CGA GTG GTT GCT GTC ATG	toxR
tdh (F)	CCA TCT GTC CCT TTT CCT GC	tdh
tdh (R)	CCA AAT ACA TTT TAC TTG G	tdh
trh (F)	GGC TCA AAA TGG TTA AGC G	trh
trh (R)	CAT TTC CGC TCT CAT ATG C	trh

(F): forward; (R): reverse.

Detection of potentially enteropathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* strains. Eighty isolates identified by biochemical tests were subjected to PCR assays to detect potentially enteropathogenic strains. All the *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates were identified as potentially enteropathogenic (Table 4).

Determination of pathogenic strains of *V. parahaemolyticus* All 80 potentially enteropathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates were tested using a PCR assay targeting the virulence genes associated with enteropathogenicity (*tdh* and *trh*). Virulotyping of *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates revealed that their prevalence varied depending on the sampling year and shellfish species. Seven pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* strains were isolated in 2013 (*tdh*+ = 2, *trh*+ = 5). None of the strains was *tdh*+ and *trh*+ (Table 4).

Comparison of *V. parahaemolyticus* prevalence and pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* strains occurrence with previous studies. We compared the *V. parahaemolyticus* occurrence and prevalence of pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* isolates with previous studies carried out in four provinces (Sassari, Oristano, Nuoro, and Cagliari) of Sardinia (Italy) between 2011 and 2018 (Marceddu et al., 2017; Sferlazzo et al., 2018; Lamón, Consolati, et al., 2019; Bazzoni et al., 2019; Lorenzoni et al., 2021). All these studies have been carried out according to well-established methods and with well-known and referenced culture media. The same conditions were used in each of the referenced studies. In comparing the results of *V. parahaemolyticus* prevalence with previous studies conducted in Sardinia (Tables 1 and 3), a high prevalence was observed in 2011 and 2012 (91.1%) and subsequently in 2016 (100%). Another decrease was observed for all the analysed samples in 2017 (8.2%) and 2018 (7.7%). Previous Italian studies reported the prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* in bivalve molluscs ranging from 34 to 100% (Ottaviani et al., 2009; Serratore et al., 2009; Carraro et al., 2015; Leoni et al., 2016). A comparison between the sampling periods 2011–2014 and 2015–2018 showed an increase in the prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* in shellfish (2011–2014 = 352, 26.6% vs. 2015–2018 = 122, 5%) (Table 5). The trend of *V. parahaemolyticus* occurrence between the two sampling periods showed a

statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in two of the four investigated provinces (Sassari and Nuoro, $p < 0.05$). By shellfish species, the prevalence in Mediterranean mussels was 88.8% in 2011–2012 and 3.5%, 2.7%, and 1% in 2013, 2014, and 2015, respectively. The highest prevalence was observed in 2016 (100%); afterward, we saw a clear decrease of 3.9% in 2017 and 1.9% in 2018 (Table 3). The trend of *V. parahaemolyticus* occurrence in Mediterranean mussels between 2011–2014 and 2015–2018 showed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the two sampling periods in two of the four investigated provinces (Sassari and Oristano, $p < 0.05$). The prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* in grooved carpet shells was 83.3% in 2011–2012, 3.5% in 2013, 2.2% in 2014, and 11.1% in 2015. As previously noted in Mediterranean mussels, the highest prevalence was recorded in 2016 (100%). The prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* positive samples was 4.1% between 2017 and 2018 (Table 3). The trend of *V. parahaemolyticus* occurrence in grooved carpet shells was significantly different ($p < 0.05$) between 2011–2014 and 2015–2018. Of the four investigated areas, only the province of Oristano showed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$). The overall percentage of Pacific cupped oysters showing positive *V. parahaemolyticus* samples was 2.5% in 2013, 0.7% in 2014, and 15.1% in 2015. No positive samples were recovered in 2017, whereas the prevalence of *V. parahaemolyticus* in 2018 was 2.5% (Table 3). The trend of *V. parahaemolyticus* occurrence in Pacific cupped oysters was significantly different between 2011–2014 and 2015–2018 ($p < 0.05$). No significant differences were observed between the four provinces. Potentially toxigenic *V. parahaemolyticus* strains (i.e. carrying *tdh* and/or *trh* genes) were recovered in low numbers, and their presence was unrelated to the total *V. parahaemolyticus* population. Overall, 208 potentially enteropathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* strains were identified through the years 2011–2018 (Fig. 2); virulotyping identified a total of 16 pathogenic strains of *V. parahaemolyticus* (7.6%). Table 4 shows the trends of potentially enteropathogenic and pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* strains occurrence during the 2011–2018 period. Ten *trh*+ and six *tdh*+ strains were identified. None of the tested strains were *tdh*+ and *trh*+. This can be attributed to two reasons. The first reason is related to their extreme rarity and difficulty of detection and the second for their reduced prevalence over time, which could be related to their occurrence in Sardinian coastal habitats during limited periods of the year. In comparing the two sampling periods (2011–2014 and 2015–2018), a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was demonstrated in the trends of potentially enteropathogenic and pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* in grooved carpet shells. Of the four investigated areas, only the province of Oristano showed a significant difference in grooved carpet shells ($p < 0.05$). In conclusion, the results of the present study fill a gap in the overview of the trends of pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* occurrence in bivalve molluscs harvested from Sardinian coastal environ-

Table 3
Distribution of the positive samples/total and prevalence (%) of *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* in shellfish from other studies carried out in Sardinia between 2011 and 2018

Reference	Year	Samples	Positive samples/sampled units (%)							
			Provinces				Species			
			Sassari	Nuoro	Oristano	Cagliari	M. galloprovincialis	R. decussatus	C. gigas	Total
Lamón, Consolati, et al. (2019) and Lamón, Bastardo, et al. (2019)*	2011	34	16/18 (88.8)	*	15/18 (83.3)	*	16/18 (88.8)	15/18 (83.3)	–	31/34 (91.1)
Lamón, Consolati, et al. (2019) and Lamón, Bastardo, et al. (2019)*	2012	34	16/18 (88.8)	*	15/18 (83.3)	*	16/18 (88.8)	15/18 (83.3)	–	31/34 (91.1)
Marceddu et al. (2017)* Sferlazzo et al. (2018)*	2016	320	300/300 (100)	*	20/20 (100)	*	300/300 (100)	20/20 (100)	–	320/320 (100)
Bazzoni et al. (2019)** Lorenzoni et al. (2021)**	2017	217	2/100 (2)	1/32 (3.1)	2/45 (4.4)	2/40 (5)	6/152 (3.9)	1/24 (4.1)	0/41 (0)	7/217 (3.2)
Bazzoni et al. (2019)** Lorenzoni et al. (2021)**	2018	218	1/104 (0.9)	1/36 (2.7)	2/48 (4.1)	1/30 (3.3)	3/154 (1.9)	1/24 (4.1)	1/40 (2.5)	5/218 (2.2)

* Own-check sampling by the FBOs in collaboration with the University of Sassari; ** Official control by the Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Sardegna

Table 4

Distribution of potentially enteropathogenic and pathogenic *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* strains in shellfish harvested in Sardinian coastal environments between 2011 and 2018

Reference	Year	<i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i> strains			
		toxR +	Pathogenic strains (tdh + /trh +)	tdh +	trh +
Lamon, Consolati, et al. (2019) and Lamon, Bastardo, et al. (2019)*	2011	57	2	1	1
Lamon, Consolati, et al. (2019) and Lamon, Bastardo, et al. (2019)*	2012	57	2	1	1
Present study**	2013	38	7	2	5
Present study**	2014	22	0	0	0
Present study**	2015	20	0	0	0
Marceddu et al. (2017)*	2016	2	2	1	1
Sferlazzo et al. (2018)*					
Bazzoni et al. (2019)**	2017	11	2	1	1
Lorenzoni et al. (2021)**					
Bazzoni et al. (2019)**	2018	1	1	0	1
Lorenzoni et al. (2021)**					
Total		208	16	6	10

* Own-check sampling by the FBOs in collaboration with the University of Sassari; ** Official control by the Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Sardegna.

Table 5

Distribution of the positive samples/total and prevalence (%) of *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* in shellfish grouped by source, investigated area and sampling period (2011–2014 vs. 2015–2018)

Sampling period	Total *	Positive samples/sampled units (%)						
		Provinces				Species		
		Sassari*	Nuoro*	Oristano	Cagliari	<i>M. galloprovincialis</i> *	<i>R. decussatus</i> *	<i>C. gigas</i> *
2011–2014	122/2,435 (5)	51/823 (6.1)	4/289 (1.3)	47/474 (9.9)	20/853 (2.3)	74/1,584 (4.6)	45/535 (8.4)	3/320 (0.9)
2015–2018	352/1,321 (26.6)	311/625 (49.7)	9/153 (5.8)	26/184 (14.1)	6/299 (2)	314/1,061 (29.5)	27/113 (23.8)	11/151 (7.2)

The asterisk (*) indicates the significant differences between the two sampling periods ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Trend of *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* pathogenic strains occurrence in shellfish harvested in Sardinian coastal environments between 2011 and 2018.

ments between 2011 and 2018. Despite the implementation of national and regional control strategies against *V. parahaemolyticus*, our results revealed that the trends in *V. parahaemolyticus* occurrence between 2011–2014 and 2015–2018 were significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Considering the risks associated with *V. parahaemolyticus* contamination, changes to EU food legislation are indispensable. According to the EC Reg. 2073/2005, currently available data do

not support the setting of specific microbiological criteria for pathogenic *V. parahaemolyticus* in shellfish. However, more stringent and specific guidelines should be established to ensure that good hygiene practices are applied during primary production and throughout the shellfish supply chain.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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